

m^{th} -Root Randers Change of a Finsler Metric

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Abstract: In this paper, we introduce a m^{th} -root Randers changed Finsler metric as

$$\bar{L}(x, y) = L(x, y) + \beta(x, y),$$

where $L = \{a_{i_1 i_2 \dots i_m}(x) y^{i_1} y^{i_2} \dots y^{i_m}\}^{\frac{1}{m}}$ is a m^{th} -root metric and β -is one form. Further we obtained the relation between the v- and hv- curvature tensor of m^{th} -root Finsler space and its m^{th} -root Randers changed Finsler space and obtained some theorems for its S3 and S4-likeness of Finsler spaces and when this changed Finsler space will be Berwald space (resp. Landsberg space). Also we obtain T-tensor for the m^{th} -root Randers changed Finsler space \bar{F}^n .

Key Words: Randers change, m^{th} -root metric, Berwald space, Landsberg space, S3 and S4-like Finsler space.

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§1. Introduction

Let $F^n = (M^n, L)$ be a n-dimensional Finsler space, whose M^n is the n-dimensional differentiable manifold and $L(x, y)$ is the Finsler fundamental function. In general, $L(x, y)$ is a function of point $x = (x^i)$ and element of support $y = (y^i)$, and positively homogeneous of degree one in y . In the year 1971 Matsumoto [6] introduced the transformations of Finsler metric given by

$$\begin{aligned} L'(x, y) &= L(x, y) + \beta(x, y) \\ L''^2(x, y) &= L^2(x, y) + \beta^2(x, y), \end{aligned}$$

where, $\beta = b_i(x) y^i$ is a one-form [1] and $b_i(x)$ are components of covariant vector which is a function of position alone. If $L(x, y)$ is a Riemannian metric, then the Finsler space with a metric $L(x, y) = \alpha(x, y) + \beta(x, y)$ is known as Randers space which is introduced by G.Randers [5]. In papers [3, 7, 8, 9], Randers spaces have been studied from a geometrical viewpoint and various theorem were obtained. In 1978, Numata [10] introduced another β -change of Finsler metric given by $L(x, y) = \mu(x, y) + \beta(x, y)$ where $\mu = \{a_{ij}(y) y^i y^j\}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is a Minkowski metric and β as above. This metric is of similar form of Randers one, but there are different tensor

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properties, because the Riemannian space with the metric α is characterized by $C_{jk}^i = 0$ and on the other hand the locally Minkowski space with the metric μ by $R_{hijk} = 0$, $C_{hij|k} = 0$.

In the year 1979, Shimada [4] introduced the concept of m^{th} root metric and developed it as an interesting example of Finsler metrics, immediately following M.Matsumoto and S.Numatas theory of cubic metrics [2]. By introducing the regularity of the metric various fundamental quantities as a Finsler metric could be found. In particular, the Cartan connection of a Finsler space with m-th root metric could be discussed from the theoretical standpoint. In 1992-1993, the m-th root metrics have begun to be applied to theoretical physics [11, 12], but the results of the investigations are not yet ready for acceding to the demands of various applications.

In the present paper we introduce a m^{th} -root Randers changed Finsler metric as

$$\bar{L}(x, y) = L(x, y) + \beta(x, y)$$

where $L = \{a_{i_1 i_2 \dots i_m}(x) y^{i_1} y^{i_2} \dots y^{i_m}\}^{\frac{1}{m}}$ is a m^{th} -root metric. This metric is of the similar form to the Randers one in the sense that the Riemannian metric is replaced with the m^{th} -root metric, due to this we call this change as m^{th} -root Randers change of the Finsler metric. Further we obtained the relation between the v-and hv-curvature tensor of m^{th} -root Finsler space and its m^{th} -root Randers changed Finsler space and obtained some theorems for its S3 and S4-likeness of Finsler spaces and when this changed Finsler space will be Berwald space (resp. Landsberg space). Also we obtain T-tensor for the m^{th} -root Randers changed Finsler space \bar{F}^n .

§2. The Fundamental Tensors of \bar{F}^n

We consider an n-dimensional Finsler space \bar{F}^n with a metric $\bar{L}(x, y)$ given by

$$\bar{L}(x, y) = L(x, y) + b_i(x) y^i \tag{1}$$

where

$$L = \{a_{i_1 i_2 \dots i_m}(x) y^{i_1} y^{i_2} \dots y^{i_m}\}^{\frac{1}{m}} \tag{2}$$

By putting

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(I). } L^{m-1} a_i(x, y) &= a_{i i_2 \dots i_m}(x) y^{i_2} y^{i_3} \dots y^{i_m} \\ \text{(II). } L^{m-2} a_{ij}(x, y) &= a_{i j i_3 i_4 \dots i_m}(x) y^{i_3} y^{i_4} \dots y^{i_m} \\ \text{(III). } L^{m-3} a_{ijk}(x, y) &= a_{i j k i_4 i_5 \dots i_m}(x) y^{i_4} y^{i_5} \dots y^{i_m} \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Now differentiating equation (1) with respect to y^i , we get the normalized supporting element $\bar{l}_i = \dot{\partial}_i \bar{L}$ as

$$\bar{l}_i = a_i + b_i \tag{4}$$

where $a_i = l_i$ is the normalized supporting element for the m^{th} -root metric. Again differentiating above equation with respect to y^j , the angular metric tensor $\bar{h}_{ij} = \bar{L} \dot{\partial}_i \dot{\partial}_j \bar{L}$ is given as

$$\frac{\bar{h}_{ij}}{\bar{L}} = \frac{h_{ij}}{L} \tag{5}$$

where h_{ij} is the angular metric tensor of m^{th} -root Finsler space with metric L given by [4]

$$h_{ij} = (m-1)(a_{ij} - a_i a_j) \quad (6)$$

The fundamental metric tensor $\bar{g}_{ij} = \dot{\partial}_i \dot{\partial}_j \frac{\bar{L}^2}{2} = \bar{h}_{ij} + \bar{l}_i \bar{l}_j$ of Finsler space F^n are obtained from equations (4), (5) and (6), which is given by

$$\bar{g}_{ij} = (m-1)\tau a_{ij} + \{1 - (m-1)\tau\}a_i a_j + (a_i b_j + a_j b_i) + b_i b_j \quad (7)$$

where $\tau = \frac{\bar{L}}{L}$. It is easy to show that

$$\dot{\partial}_i \tau = \frac{\{(1-\tau)a_i + b_i\}}{L}, \quad \dot{\partial}_j a_i = \frac{(m-1)(a_{ij} - a_i a_j)}{L}, \quad \dot{\partial}_k a_{ij} = \frac{(m-2)(a_{ijk} - a_{ij} a_k)}{L}$$

Therefore from (7), it follows (h)hv-torsion tensor $\bar{C}_{ijk} = \dot{\partial}_k \frac{\bar{g}_{ij}}{2}$ of the Cartan's connection CT are given by

$$\begin{aligned} 2L\bar{C}_{ijk} &= (m-1)(m-2)\tau a_{ijk} + [\{1 - (m-1)\tau\}(m-1)](a_{ij} a_k \\ &\quad + a_{jk} a_i + a_{ki} a_j) + (m-1)(a_{ij} b_k + a_{jk} b_i + a_{ki} b_j) - \\ &\quad (m-1)(a_i a_j b_k + a_j a_k b_i + a_i a_k b_j) + (m-1)\{(2m-1)\tau - 3\}a_i a_j a_k \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

In view of equation (6) the equation (8) may be written as

$$\bar{C}_{ijk} = \tau C_{ijk} + \frac{(h_{ij} m_k + h_{jk} m_i + h_{ki} m_j)}{2L} \quad (9)$$

where $m_i = b_i - \frac{\beta}{L} a_i$ and C_{ijk} is the (h)hv-torsion tensor of the Cartan's connection CT of the m^{th} -root Finsler metric L given by

$$2LC_{ijk} = (m-1)(m-2)\{a_{ijk} - (a_{ij} a_k + a_{jk} a_i + a_{ki} a_j) + 2a_i a_j a_k\} \quad (10)$$

Let us suppose that the intrinsic metric tensor $a_{ij}(x, y)$ of the m^{th} -root metric L has non-vanishing determinant. Then the inverse matrix (a^{ij}) of (a_{ij}) exists. Therefore the reciprocal metric tensor \bar{g}^{ij} of \bar{F}^n is obtain from equation (7) which is given by

$$\bar{g}^{ij} = \frac{1}{(m-1)\tau} a^{ij} + \frac{b^2 + (m-1)\tau - 1}{(m-1)\tau(1+q)^2} a^i a^j - \frac{(a^i b^j + a^j b^i)}{(m-1)\tau(1+q)} \quad (11)$$

where $a^i = a^{ij} a_j$, $b^i = a^{ij} b_j$, $b^2 = b^i b_i$, $q = a^i b_i = a_i b^i = \beta/L$.

Proposition 2.1 *The normalized supporting element l_i , angular metric tensor h_{ij} , metric tensor g_{ij} and (h)hv-torsion tensor C_{ijk} of Finsler space with m^{th} -root Randers changed metric are given by (4), (5), (7) and (9) respectively.*

§3. The v -Curvature Tensor of \bar{F}^n

From (6), (10) and definition of m_i and a^i , we get the following identities

$$\begin{aligned} a^i a_i &= 1, & a_{ijk} a^i &= a_{jk}, & C_{ijk} a^i &= 0, & h_{ij} a^i &= 0, \\ m_i a^i &= 0, & h_{ij} b^j &= 3m_i, & m_i b^i &= (b^2 - q^2) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

To find the v -curvature tensor of F^n , we first find (h)hv-torsion tensor $\bar{C}_{jk}^i = \bar{g}^{ir} \bar{C}_{jrk}$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{C}_{jk}^i &= \frac{1}{m-1} C_{jk}^i + \frac{1}{2(m-1)\bar{L}} (h_j^i m_k + h_k^i m_j + h_{jk} m^i) - \\ &\quad \frac{a^i}{\bar{L}(1+q)} \left\{ m_j m_k + \frac{1}{(m-1)(m-2)} h_{jk} \right\} - \frac{1}{(m-1)(1+q)} a^i C_{jrk} b^r \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where $LC_{jk}^i = LC_{jrk} a^{ir} = (m-1) \{ a_{jk}^i - (\delta_j^i a_k + \delta_k^i a_j + a^i a_{jk}) + 2a^i a_j a_k \}$,

$$\begin{aligned} h_j^i &= h_{jr} a^{ir} = (m-1) (\delta_j^i - a^i a_j) \\ m^i &= m_r a^{ir} = b^i - q a^i, \quad \text{and} \quad a_{jk}^i = a^{ir} a_{jrk} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

From (12) and (14), we have the following identities

$$\begin{aligned} C_{ijr} h_p^r &= C_{ij}^r h_{pr} = (m-1) C_{ijp}, \quad C_{ijr} m^r = C_{ijr} b^r, \\ m_r h_i^r &= (m-1) m_i, \quad m_i m^i = (b^2 - q^2), \\ h_{ir} h_j^r &= (m-1) h_{ij}, \quad h_{ir} m^r = (m-1) m_i \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

From (9) and (13), we get after applying the identities (15)

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{C}_{ijr} \bar{C}_{hk}^r &= \frac{\tau}{(m-1)} C_{ijr} C_{hk}^r + \frac{1}{2\bar{L}} (C_{ijh} m_k + C_{ijk} m_h + C_{hjk} m_i + C_{hik} m_j) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2(m-1)} (C_{ijr} h_{hk} + C_{hrk} h_{ij}) b^r + \frac{1}{4(m-1)\bar{L}\bar{L}} (b^2 - q^2) h_{ij} h_{hk} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{4\bar{L}\bar{L}} (2h_{ij} m_h m_k + 2h_{kh} m_i m_j + h_{jh} m_i m_k \\ &\quad + h_{jk} m_i m_h + h_{ih} m_j m_k + h_{ik} m_j m_h) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Now we shall find the v -curvature tensor $\bar{S}_{hijk} = \bar{C}_{ijr} \bar{C}_{hk}^r - \bar{C}_{ikr} \bar{C}_{hj}^r$. The tensor is obtained from (16) and given by

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{S}_{hijk} &= \Theta_{(jk)} \left\{ \frac{\tau}{m-1} C_{ijr} C_{hk}^r + h_{ij} m_{hk} + h_{hk} m_{ij} \right\} \\ &= \frac{\tau}{(m-1)} S_{hijk} + \Theta_{(jk)} \{ h_{ij} m_{hk} + h_{hk} m_{ij} \} \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where

$$m_{ij} = \frac{1}{2(m-1)\bar{L}} \left\{ C_{ijr} b^r + \frac{(b^2 - q^2)}{4\bar{L}} h_{ij} + \frac{(m-1)}{2} \bar{L}^{-1} m_i m_j \right\} \quad (18)$$

and the symbol $\Theta_{(jk)} \{ \dots \}$ denotes the exchange of j, k and subtraction.

Proposition 3.1 *The v -curvature tensor \bar{S}_{hijk} of m^{th} -root Randers changed Finsler space \bar{F}^n with respect to Cartan's connection CT is of the form (17).*

It is well known [13] that the v -curvature tensor of any three-dimensional Finsler space is of the form

$$L^2 S_{hijk} = S (h_{hj} h_{ik} - h_{hk} h_{ij}) \quad (19)$$

Owing to this fact M. Matsumoto [13] defined the S3-like Finsler space F^n ($n \geq 3$) as such a Finsler space in which v -curvature tensor is of the form (19). The scalar S in (19) is a function of x alone.

The v -curvature tensor of any four-dimensional Finsler space may be written as [13]

$$L^2 S_{hijk} = \Theta_{(jk)} \{h_{hj} K_{ki} + h_{ik} K_{hj}\} \quad (20)$$

where K_{ij} is a $(0, 2)$ type symmetric Finsler tensor field which is such that $K_{ij}y^j = 0$. A Finsler space F^n ($n \geq 4$) is called S_4 -like Finsler space [13] if its v -curvature tensor is of the form (20).

From (17), (19), (20) and (5) we have the following theorems.

Theorem 3.1 *The m^{th} -root Randers changed S_3 -like or S_4 -like Finsler space is S_4 -like Finsler space.*

Theorem 3.2 *If v -curvature tensor of m^{th} -root Randers changed Finsler space \bar{F}^n vanishes, then the Finsler space with m^{th} -root metric F^n is S_4 -like Finsler space.*

If v -curvature tensor of Finsler space with m^{th} -root metric F^n vanishes then equation (17) reduces to

$$\bar{S}_{hijk} = h_{ij}m_{hk} + h_{hk}m_{ij} - h_{ik}m_{hj} - h_{hj}m_{ik} \quad (21)$$

By virtue of (21) and (11) and the Ricci tensor $\bar{S}_{ik} = \bar{g}^{hk}\bar{S}_{hijk}$ is of the form

$$\bar{S}_{ik} = \left(-\frac{1}{(m-1)\tau}\right)\{mh_{ik} + (m-1)(n-3)m_{ik}\},$$

where $m = m_{ij}a^{ij}$, which in view of (18) may be written as

$$\bar{S}_{ik} + H_1 h_{ik} + H_2 C_{ikr} b^r = H_3 m_i m_k, \quad (22)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} H_1 &= \frac{m}{(m-1)\tau} + \frac{(n-3)(b^2 - q^2)}{8(m-1)\bar{L}^2}, \\ H_2 &= \frac{(n-3)}{2(m-1)\bar{L}}, \\ H_3 &= -\frac{(n-3)}{2\bar{L}^2}. \end{aligned}$$

From (22), we have the following

Theorem 3.3 *If v -curvature tensor of m^{th} -root Randers changed Finsler space \bar{F}^n vanishes then there exist scalar H_1 and H_2 in Finsler space with m^{th} -root metric F^n ($n \geq 4$) such that matrix $\|\bar{S}_{ik} + H_1 h_{ik} + H_2 C_{ikr} b^r\|$ is of rank two.*

§4. The $(v)hv$ -Torsion Tensor and hv -Curvature Tensor of \bar{F}^n

Now we concerned with $(v)hv$ -torsion tensor P_{ijk} and hv -curvature tensor P_{hijk} . With respect to the Cartan connection CT , $L_{|i} = 0$, $l_{i|j} = 0$, $h_{ij|k} = 0$ hold good [13].

Taking h -covariant derivative of equation (9) and using (4) and $l_i = a_i = 0$ we have

$$\bar{C}_{ijk|h} = \tau C_{ijk|h} + \frac{b_{i|h}}{L} C_{ijk} + \frac{(h_{ij}b_{k|h} + h_{jk}b_{i|h} + h_{ki}b_{j|h})}{2L} \quad (23)$$

From equation (6) and using relation $h_{ij|h} = 0$ We have

$$a_{ij|h} = 0, \quad \text{and} \quad a_{ijk|h} = \frac{2LC_{ijk|h}}{(m-1)(m-2)} \quad (24)$$

The $(v)hv$ -torsion tensor P_{ijk} and the hv -curvature tensor P_{hijk} of the Cartan connection CT are written in the form, respectively

$$P_{ijk} = C_{ijk|0}, \quad (25)$$

$$P_{hijk} = C_{ijk|h} - C_{hjk|i} + P_{ikr}C_{jk}^r - P_{hkr}C_{ji}^r$$

where the subscript '0' means the contraction for the supporting element y^i . Therefore the $(v)hv$ -torsion tensor \bar{P}_{ijk} and the hv -curvature tensor \bar{P}_{hijk} of the Cartan connection CT for the Finsler space with m^{th} -root Randers metric by using (10), (23), (24) and (25) we have

$$\bar{P}_{ijk} = \frac{(m-1)(m-2)}{2L} \tau a_{ijk|0} + \frac{b_{i|0}}{L} C_{ijk} + \frac{(h_{ij}b_{k|0} + h_{jk}b_{i|0} + h_{ki}b_{j|0})}{2L} \quad (26)$$

and

$$\bar{P}_{hijk} = (m-1)(m-2)(2L)^{-1} \Theta_{(jk)}(a_{ijk|h} + \bar{P}_{ikr}\bar{C}_{jh}^r) \quad (27)$$

Definition 4.1([13]) *A Finsler space is called a Berwald space (resp. Landsberg space) if $C_{ijk|h} = 0$ (resp. $P_{ijk} = 0$) holds good.*

Consequently, from (24) and (26) we have

Theorem 4.1 *A Finsler space with the m^{th} -root Randers changed metric is a Berwald space (resp. Landsberg space), if and only if $a_{ijk|h} = 0$ (resp. $a_{ijk|0} = 0$ and $b_{i|h}$ is covariantly constant.*

Proposition 4.1 *The $v(hv)$ -torsion tensor and hv -curvature tensor \bar{P}_{hijk} of m^{th} -root Randers changed Finsler space \bar{F}^n with respect to Cartan's connection CT is of the form (26) and (27).*

§5. T-Tensor of \bar{F}^n

Now, the T-tensor is given by [11,13]

$$T_{hijk} = LC_{hij|k} + l_i C_{hjk} + l_j C_{hik} + l_k C_{hij} + l_h C_{ijk}$$

The above equation for m^{th} -root Randers changed Finsler space \bar{F}^n is given as

$$\bar{T}_{hijk} = \bar{L}\bar{C}_{hij|k} + \bar{l}_i \bar{C}_{hjk} + \bar{l}_j \bar{C}_{hik} + \bar{l}_k \bar{C}_{hij} + \bar{l}_h \bar{C}_{ijk} \quad (28)$$

The v -derivative of h_{ij} and L is given by [13]

$$h_{ij|k} = -\frac{1}{L}(h_{ik}l_j + h_{jk}l_i), \quad \text{and} \quad L|i = l_i \quad (29)$$

Now using (29), the v-derivative of C_{ijk} is given as

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{L}\bar{C}_{ijk}|_h &= \tau \frac{(Lb_h - \beta l_h)}{L} C_{ijk} + \bar{L}\tau C_{ijk}|_h - \tau \frac{1}{2L} (h_{ih}l_j m_k + h_{jh}l_i m_k \\ &\quad + h_{jh}l_k m_i + h_{kh}l_j m_i + h_{ih}l_k m_j + h_{kh}l_i m_j + h_{ij}l_h m_k \\ &\quad + h_{jk}l_h m_i + h_{ki}l_h m_j) + \frac{\tau}{2} (h_{ij}m_k|_h + h_{jk}m_i|_h + h_{ki}m_j|_h) \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

Using (4), (9) and (30), the T-tensor for m^{th} -root Randers changed Finsler space \bar{F}^n is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{T}_{hijk} &= \tau(T_{hijk} + B_{hijk}) + \frac{\tau}{2L} (h_{jk}m_h l_i + h_{ik}m_h l_j + h_{ij}m_h l_k \\ &\quad + h_{ki}m_j l_h) + \frac{1}{2L} (h_{hj}m_k b_i + h_{jk}m_h b_i + h_{kh}m_j b_i + h_{ik}m_h b_j \\ &\quad + h_{ih}m_k b_j + h_{kh}m_i b_j + h_{ij}m_h b_k + h_{ih}m_j b_k + h_{jh}m_i b_k + h_{ij}m_k b_h \\ &\quad + h_{ki}m_j b_h + h_{jk}m_i b_h) + \frac{\tau}{2} (h_{ij}m_k|_h + h_{jk}m_i|_h + h_{ki}m_j|_h) \\ &\quad + \tau \frac{(Lb_h - \beta l_h)}{L} C_{ijk} \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

where $B_{hijk} = \beta C_{hij|k} + b_i C_{hjk} + b_j C_{hik} + b_k C_{hij} + b_h C_{ijk}$. Thus, we know

Proposition 5.1 *The T-tensor \bar{T}_{hijk} for m^{th} -root Randers changed Finsler space \bar{F}^n is given by (31).*

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